

Figshare

Description

Figshare allows academics and researchers to upload their research data and other digital outputs in an easily accessible format that is available for use through a Creative Commons license. The service is free for academics and is designed to improve their workflow processes and increase citations of their work. The business model is based on a value-add offering of customisation of services to institutions and publishers of open source data.

Services offered to institutions and other organizations include customisation and branding of materials, data management, metrics, dissemination services and user group management. Publishers are able to upload additional resources that are related to journal articles which then provides direct links back to the journal article along with data visualisation tools. In addition to these services, the company also offers cloud based storage solutions that enable publishers to maintain access to all published journal articles without impact to their data infrastructure. The third party outsourcing of mandated data management is a viable and economic way to ensure that open access to data meets the requirements of funders and increases access to individuals, incentivising data use and reuse.

Figshare continues to evolve and offer researchers and institutions new ways to organise and manage their research outputs. Launched in March of 2016, the new 'Collections' tool allows users to set up virtual pin boards where data and other research outputs can be grouped together in much the same fashion as the social media site Pinterest. Collections can be made private or shared with collaborators and the general public.

Economic benefits

Utilising the power of cloud-based data management, Figshare removes the need for higher learning institutions to build and fund their own IT infrastructure to support a robust research data management plan. The cost savings are immediate as researchers can capture their data and simultaneously upload it to Figshare at no cost, eliminating time spent saving, categorising and managing files on internal servers. The majority of costs associated with implementing a research data management plan are related to staff time, often at the senior administrative level, to implement policy directives and funder mandates. Over time and with use of platforms like Figshare, the time required by institutions along with the cost of maintaining an open access program will be reduced.

Supporting links

What is an open business model and how can you generate revenue?' http://bit.ly/Open_Business_Model Accessed 04 April 2016.

www.figshare.com Accessed 27 April 2016.

'Solving the research data management problem for educational research institutions' http://bit.ly/Solving_RDM Accessed 05 May 2016.

'Figshare launches Collections - a "Pinterest" for academic research outputs' http://bit.ly/Figshare_Launches_Collections Accessed 05 May 2016.

'Counting the costs of open access' http://bit.ly/Open_Access_Cost Accessed 05 May 2016.

'Preserving research: the top online archives for storing your unpublished findings' http://bit.ly/Preserving_Research Accessed 05 May 2016.